

ISic0768

Dedication by a sevir to Concordia

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

marble (white)

Object

base

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated 10 September 1970, in front of room 2 of the west portico of the agora; found in contact with the pavement of the portico

Coordinates

37.998047, 14.262635

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 20226

Physical Description

Large fragment of white marble, broken on all sides. The lower surface is crudely finished; the upper surface is smooth and preserves a hole for a fixing pin on the left.

Dimensions

Height 8.5 cm

Width 41 cm

Depth 21 cm

Layout

The epigraphic face is preserved for a width of 12.5 cm, with two lines of Latin letters filling the available field.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are tall, neatly cut and closely spaced (height c.30mm), and words are separated by simple triangular interpuncts. The letters are lightly serified. E is tall and narrow, T has a curved cross-bar, rising to the right.

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: ? mm

Text

1. [---][Conco]rdiae · Aug[ustae][---]

2. [---]ethus · sev[ir][---]

Apparatus

Text based on autopsy

Translation (en)

[---]to Augustan Concord[---(set up by) -]ethus, sevir[---]

Commentary

The fragment is likely to have formed part of the base of a statue, a dedication by a sevir. The extent of the text to left and right cannot be established. As previous editors have noted, Augustan concord is often associated with pax (for which see ISic3576 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3576>]) or spes and one of those may have stood in the first part of line 1 (Portale 2009: 85 n.46). The full name of the sevir must have stood in the latter part of line 1 and/or the first part of line 2. Manganaro (1989: 190, under no.80) suggested that this could be Aulus Mevius Zethus, known from another inscription from Halaesa (ISic0767 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0767>]) and plausibly restored the text as: Concordiae Augustae sacrum | A(ulus) Mevius Zethus sevir Augustalis, i.e. "Sacred to Augustan Concord. Aulus Mevius Zethus, sevir Augustalis (set this up)".

The inscription was found in the same area of the portico as an acephalous statue of a female figure found in 1895 (inv. 20193; Portale 2009: 80 n.30 and 82 n.36), not dissimilar to the statue of Ceres dedicated by another sevir (ISic0804 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0804>]). Portale (2009: 85-87) has suggested that the inscription should be associated with the statue, which would then be a representation of Concord. The statue is dated stylistically to the early Antonine period (140s BC), about a generation earlier than the statue of Ceres. Such a date would be entirely compatible with the form of the inscription, which could be later first or second century AD (and that of Mevius Zethus could be first or second century also). The inscribed base and statue would presumably originally have stood in a niche in one of the rooms of the portico.

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